

Entrepreneur Certified Blockchain professional and Coach in personal finance

Camille Lagueu^a

^a *Blockchain Institute of Technology, Montreal, Quebec, Canada*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

An increasingly changing world dominated by the digital ecosystem. The fourth industrial revolution is underway and Blockchain technology is one of the key pillars; some have dubbed it the "machine to create trust".

2. Aim

The Blockchain is a decentralized and distributed digital ledger which records data or transactions continuously without the possibility of modifications or deletion once approved.

3. Material and methods

A disruptive innovation greater than or equal to the of Internet in the 90s in line with TCP / IP (Internet communications), SMTP (email), or FTP (file transfer). Blockchain stands out as a tool or medium for transferring values or properties over internet. Blockchain as a solution its requirements for business: - Distributed ledger, recording system distributed by adding - only to share through the business network - Confidentiality Ensured appropriate visibility transactions are secure, authenticated and verifiable. - Smart Contract: Business terms embedded in the transaction database and executed with transactions. - Trust: Transactions are approved by the relevant participants.

4. Results

- Time saving: transaction time, from day to almost instantaneous
- Cost reduction: overhead, structure and intermediary costs
- Risk reduction: Handling, fraud and cybercrime
- Gain of trust: Through shared resources and the maintenance of a common registry

February 3, 2018

5. Conclusions

In the light of the above, there is a need for Key players in blockchain adoption; such as entrepreneurs, academics, Industrial and corporate group and especially Regulator / Government Authority.

6. Keywords

Blockchain technology; Bitcoin; Cryptocurrencies; Smart Contract: Decentralization

Author biography

Camille Lagueu Camille has completed his BBA and Master degree at Intec-Cnam of Paris and has passed many certificates in finance, digital marketing and Blockchain technology. He is the Senior Vice President, Francophone African Market Operations with <https://www.surebanqa.services/> which aims to launch an ICO to develop a platform on blockchain technology to help the unbanked, underbanked and underserved in developing countries to become financial inclusive and run their own bank. He has many years of work experience with several companies in